

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report summarizing experiences and recommendations (workflow stock-taking) of Cycle 1 and 2 Hackathons
Deliverable number	D15 (Del. Rel. No. D2.3)
Revision	0
Status	Draft
Planned delivery date	31/12/2022
Actual date of issue	31/01/2023
Nature of deliverable	Other
Lead partner	MPI-M
Dissemination level	Report

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

This report will document the experiences regarding the use of the SR-ESM simulation analysis workflow at the Hackathons (what worked what did not work) and the recommendations made by Hackathon participants to improve these workflows.

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WP2

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1 Executive summary

2 Conclusion & Results

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP2	Relevance in this deliverable?
Organizing simulation output from the pre-existing ICON and IFS DYAMOND-Winter simulations (Cycle 1 simulations) (O1)	no
To perform the Cycle 2 and initiate the Cycle 3 simulations of the Development Phase (Fig. 2) (O1)	yes
To address errors and fine-tune the SR-ESMs, including associated output and data management strategies, based on feedback from, and together with, the S&R, S&O, S&L themes (O1)	no

Objectives of WP2

Relevance in this deliverable?

To implement selected applications in SR-ESMs in collaboration with the four themes and users (O3)

no

To organise scrums to address data management and data analysis workflows in support of Hackathons and simulations analysis within NextGEMS and beyond (O1)

yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Workflow analysis for Cycle 1 Hackathon

Lessons learned from the Cycle 1 Hackathon

Overall, the Cycle 1 Hackathon was a great success: 96 scientists from 24 institutions gathered at Harnack Haus in Berlin and spent four days analyzing the latest simulations performed with IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO and ICON. Scientists were organised in several topics per nextGEMS research themes.

By providing all participants with DKRZ accounts via a dedicated analysis project bb1153, we could ensure that all participants had access to the data sets and could make use of the MIS-TRAL supercomputer of DKRZ for analysis with jupyterhub notebooks or other means, such as shell (script) based approaches.

The success of the Hackathon can also be attributed to the effort that was spent on preparing the data by splitting it by variable and day, and by renaming variables to common names. However, this process also proved tedious and impractical for the growing amounts of data expected for the follow-up cycles and hackathons. Often, seemingly analogous variables are defined slightly different between the models, e. g. their units or reference values. Also, some of the simulations were finished just in time for the hackathon, so there was minimal time available for the standardization. We therefore decided not to repeat this step, but unify the access in other ways.

The Intake catalog, providing semantic and format independent access, proved to be promising but uptake was limited during the hackathon. This is partly due to the examples not covering all of the relevant use-cases. Furthermore, many users are still tied to shell-script based workflows and were missing a simple access to the catalog information.

Together with the H2020 project ESIWACE2, we provide [easy.gems](#) as central documentation hub (see D2.1). This proved very helpful for the hackathon work, as did the shared use of the dedicated project bb1153. Based on the good experience, both were continued and expanded for the Cycle 2 hackathon.

Data usage focused on the higher resolution data, but for many analyses, it also proved useful to interpolate data to regular grids instead of working on the model's native grid.

At the same time, the output data contained some redundancies and unfortunate choices, e. g. quantities that could as well be derived from others, or high accuracy that ultimately was not exploited, e. g. very high frequency 3D output, or atmospheric output on model levels instead of pressure level as used in atmosphere observations. The inappropriateness of the latter was also underlined by the frequent requests to have data converted accordingly.

4.2 Update analysis workflows for the Cycle 2 Hackathon

The Cycle 2 Hackathon in Vienna continued the success of the first hackathon: 92 scientists from 22 institutions gathered in Vienna and spent five days analyzing the latest simulations performed with IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO and ICON. Participants focused their analyses on two topics per

nextGEMS research theme, with a special focus topic on solar and wind energy. All nextGEMS data and the associated processing environment had been moved to the new supercomputer Levante at DKRZ for the Cycle 2 Hackathon.

Implementation of lessons learned from Cycle 1

Standardization We had a 2 day meeting of the data team before the hackathon to prepare harmonized data access methods. One of the challenges here was providing access to the IFS data in its native grib format. The grib files data were combined into coherent zarr data sets and included in the overall catalog making use of a newly developed tool *gribscan*¹.

Intake The catalog search options were reviewed and extended to provide for more use-cases. Generation of catalog data was changed to be provided natively by ICON experiment jobs. IFS data were inserted via *gribscan* (see above). To extend the options for scientific analysis, a command line interface (*find_files*) for querying the catalog was added.

Documentation The *easy.gems* documentation hub was re-structured and extended. This comprised visual separation of technical and more general topics, additional and more concise examples and a dedicated introduction to the data and methods to use it. The examples at *easy.gems* were complemented with additional examples at github.com (see [easy.gems Processing](#) Section).

To ease the start of the analysis, we preceded the main Cycle 2 hackathon with an additional data introduction day, presenting the improved Intake catalog and *easy.gems* examples, plus tutelage on their use and extension for own analyses.

Data Usage The model output was reduced to remove implicit redundancies and to make efficient use of the data storage by adjusting the output frequencies to better match their envisioned use-cases, and by using vertical interpolation of 3D atmosphere output to selected pressure levels. To allow effective data overview, we provided interpolated data as monthly means on a regular grid with reduced spatial resolution for key model quantities.

Lessons learned from the Cycle 2 Hackathon

Data Access methods and updated Intake catalog were accepted well. Combining data from different models was still technically challenging due to differences in internal definition of 3d and time structure.

The revised documentation and new introduction was much appreciated, and appears to have played an important part in the broad adoption of the techniques described above. While the technical documentation was widely lauded, documentation of the scientific properties and setup details of each experiment was not complete and was missed when interpreting combined data from different experiments.

Even with reduced output compared to Cycle 1, storage requirements were still large, also because some of the 3d ICON atmosphere data had to be stored at model levels due to the physical interpretation of the vertical velocities.

¹<https://gribscan.readthedocs.io/>

For effective use of the storage resources, much of the data was made available in compressed format (netCDF deflate). However, accessing compressed data in vertical profile or regional fashion was inefficient due to the data being stored in one storage block (chunk) per global 2d data set, and the decompression only being able to work on full chunks.

4.3 Update analysis workflows for the Cycle 3 Hackathon

Proposals from lessons learned of Cycle 2

Experiment Documentation Contents and form should have a similar standard across all experiments.

Compression, Chunks We currently are experimenting with the trade-off between chunk structure and compression, to allow fast regional data access as well as non-degrading global access. To further reduce storage, the use of rounding output data to scientifically significant bits, specific to the different quantities, is currently explored. Furthermore, we are studying more advanced compression algorithms provided via the HDF5 backend of netCDF4, that promise faster decompression at similar compression rates.

Data Storage, Intake Data storage requirements will force us to use a hierarchical model including tape archiving of low-access data together with disk or object storage access for data in frequent use. The intake catalog allows us to implement this hierarchical model while hiding its complexity from the users performing the analysis.

Data Access Towards a common structure for analysis, we will explore use of common grid for both models, as well as the possibility to provide data in different horizontal resolutions instead of just a fixed low-resolution overview version.

These proposed changes will be implemented and tested in 'beta' runs of reduced length.

5 References (Bibliography)

Not applicable.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)

	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?
yes

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.4. - 3.4.2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26.06. - 02.07. in Vienna
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>